

SmartCorners

D5.1

Innovative predictive control solutions supported by fleet data (v1)

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1 Executive Summary

This report presents the interim results of Work Package 5 (WP5) “Optimal, safe and secure operation on vehicle level” of the SmartCorners project. It emphasizes the development and initial validation of new predictive control solutions for a battery electric vehicle (BEV) equipped with four smart e-corner modules. These modules combine in-wheel motors (IWMs), brake-by-wire, and advanced suspension and kinematic actuators at each wheel. This setup allows for distributed actuation and offers new avenues for energy-efficient, safe, and comfortable vehicle operation throughout its lifespan.

In this context, Deliverable D5.1 “Innovative predictive control solutions supported by fleet data” outlines the status at M24 of two main activities: Task T5.1, which develops predictive integrated chassis control for the SmartCorners electric vehicle (EV), and Task T5.2, which enhances vehicle-level control with a mission-management layer that uses fleet data and off-board computation. The findings presented here translate the project's high-level goals of energy efficiency, safety, comfort, robustness, and user value into specific control concepts, quantitative key performance indicators (KPIs), and a control architecture that can be implemented on the demonstrator vehicle and connected test fleets.

Section 2 introduces the motivation and technical background, explaining how current EV architectures are limited by separately designed propulsion, braking, suspension, and steering systems. It shows how smart e-corners with IWMs and by-wire interfaces enable more integrated and user-focused control strategies. It also situates WP5 within the entire SmartCorners project, where advanced control and the use of artificial intelligence (AI)-driven data are crucial for fully leveraging the new hardware design.

Section 3 summarizes the technical requirements guiding Tasks T5.1 and T5.2, including limitations from the SmartCorners vehicle architecture, multi-criteria control goals (safety, energy efficiency, thermal limits, comfort, tire and component usage, robustness, and real-time feasibility), and how on-board, contextual, and fleet data play a role in supporting predictive and mission-level decisions.

Section 4 describes the overall control architecture. It is organized hierarchically into actuator, coordinated chassis/powertrain, supervisory, and mission-management layers, and includes functions for diagnostics, safety, cybersecurity, and data logging. The architecture follows a “local autonomy plus remote intelligence” model: all safety-critical, real-time control loops operate on board, while intensive learning and optimization tasks are carried out off board using cloud resources and fleet data. Clear interfaces are established between the on-board system, the off-board analytics platform, and the digital-twin and X-in-the-Loop (XiL) environments from other WPs, ensuring traceability from simulation to vehicle implementation.

Section 5 explains the concepts and intended implementation of predictive integrated chassis control developed in Task T5.1. Based on a full-vehicle model that includes IWMs, active suspension, and wheel-kinematic actuators, the approach uses a nonlinear model predictive controller (NMPC) to coordinate wheel torques, vertical forces, and kinematic angles within a unified optimization framework. Predictive use of map and advanced driver assistance system (ADAS) information enables proactive body control, better torque vectoring (TV), improved grip utilization, and lower energy consumption through rolling-resistance and ride-height optimization. To meet real-time demands on automotive electronic control units (ECUs), the

project uses surrogate models based on neural networks (NNs) and imitation learning (IL), allowing NMPC behaviour to be approximated with significantly less computational cost while maintaining accuracy.

Section 6 describes the mission-control concepts supported by the fleet and initial implementation steps in Task T5.2. Building on the “Virtual Active Rollbar” concept developed in earlier work, the IWMs generate roll-controlling vertical force vectoring (FV) while a dual-loop architecture combines a fast reactive layer with a predictive roll-control layer. A slip-control function supervises IWM torques, ensuring safe tire-force use and providing continuous estimates of local tire–road friction. These grip estimates, along with comfort-related KPIs and contextual information, are sent to a cloud-based analytics platform and compiled into a “road-intelligence” layer. Vehicles can then get compact road descriptions, such as expected friction and roughness along a route, and use them to adjust predictive roll control ahead of critical segments. This improves ride comfort and consistency while ensuring safety even with unreliable connectivity. Initial tests on the demonstrator confirm that predictive roll control with IWM-based vertical FV is viable on the vehicle and shows comfort improvements in line with previous simulations.

Section 7 connects these technical advancements to the overall SmartCorners goals, milestones, and expected impacts. D5.1 is a key verification element for Milestone 4 “Control strategy available” at M24, showing that essential predictive control and fleet-data concepts have moved from design to functioning implementations and initial vehicle validation.

Section 8 concludes the report, noting that no critical issues affecting Tasks T5.1 and T5.2 have been identified at this stage and outlines the plan toward Deliverable D5.4 at M34, where the fully integrated, end-to-end concept—including fleet-data collection, cloud-based model updating, and vehicle-side use of road-intelligence inputs—will be demonstrated and reported along with consolidated KPI-based evaluations.

2 Introduction

The rapid shift to EVs is changing how cars are designed, controlled, and operated. BEVs play a key role in Europe’s plans to cut carbon emissions, reduce air pollution, and improve energy security. However, despite significant advances in engine efficiency and battery technology, current EV setups still face challenges with range, cost, comfort, and user flexibility. Many of these issues arise from outdated design methods, where propulsion, braking, suspension, and steering are developed as mostly separate systems and integrated later in the vehicle development process.

IWMs provide a promising way to address these challenges. By placing the motor directly inside the wheel, IWMs save space in the chassis and allow for new design concepts. They also enable finer control of wheel torque. When paired with steer-by-wire, brake-by-wire, and advanced suspension systems, IWMs can be combined into compact, multifunctional “e-corner” modules that integrate propulsion, braking, and chassis functions at each wheel. This distributed control creates new opportunities for energy-efficient vehicle operation, improved safety and comfort, as well as flexible skateboard-like platforms that can meet various uses and body styles.

At the same time, vehicle operation is becoming more data-driven. Modern EVs constantly generate data about components, operating conditions, driver behaviour, and the

environment. When this data is combined with historical fleet information and external sources like traffic, weather, and infrastructure, it lays the groundwork for data-driven design and control methods enhanced by AI. These methods can help optimize multiple factors such as energy efficiency, thermal management, durability, comfort, safety, and environmental impact rather than just focusing on individual components.

The SmartCorners project builds on these trends by aiming for a user-focused optimal design of EVs with smart e-corner modules. Its main idea is that combining advanced e-corner hardware with AI-based control can significantly improve performance and user value compared to traditional EV setups. On the hardware side, SmartCorners seeks to develop highly integrated e-corner modules using IWMs and compact chassis actuators. On the software side, the project is working on adaptive control and energy management strategies that leverage vehicle and fleet data to continually enhance operation throughout the vehicle's life.

This integrated approach tackles several important challenges. First, energy and thermal management must work together across power electronics, electric machines, battery, and cabin systems to maximize range and prolong component life under real-world conditions. Second, vehicle dynamics control should utilize the distributed capabilities of e-corners, such as individual wheel TV and predictive body control, while ensuring reliability and safety. Third, new design methods are needed to take full advantage of the flexible design offered by skateboard-like platforms and align vehicle concepts with user demands, manufacturing limits, and end-of-life issues like dismantling and recycling.

3 Technical Background and Requirements

This section summarizes the technical context for the development of D5.1 control solutions. It identifies the main requirements that guide the work in Tasks T5.1 and T5.2. It connects the capabilities and limitations of the SmartCorners vehicle architecture with the goals of predictive operation at the vehicle level and mission control based on fleet data.

The focus is on three main areas: the vehicle and SmartCorners architecture where the control functions operate, the control goals and performance measures that the solutions must meet, and the data and fleet use cases that support the mission-control ideas. Together, these areas provide the framework for the design, implementation, and validation activities discussed in the rest of D5.1.

3.1 Vehicle and SmartCorners Architecture

The SmartCorners concept is built on a BEV platform that features four integrated e-corner modules, known as “smart corners.” Each smart corner combines propulsion, braking, and chassis functions at the wheel level. It is also designed to work with a centralized vehicle control system and, when needed, with off-board services.

At a basic level, each smart corner has an IWM that provides electric traction and regenerative braking. It includes an electromechanical or electro-hydraulic brake system that works with the in-wheel motor for brake blending. It also features active suspension or ride-height actuation for vertical force control and body management. Additionally, it has wheel kinematic adjustments, which allow for toe and camber modifications to optimize tire use and rolling resistance. Local sensing for wheel speeds, suspension movement, and temperatures, along

with local control electronics, support these functions. Communication interfaces connect each module to the vehicle's domain controller.

In this architecture, the control functions developed in WP5 are structured hierarchically. At the actuator level, local controllers manage the safe operation of each actuator, like torque control IWMs and force control for suspension systems. At the chassis and powertrain level, functions such as TV, vertical force distribution, and wheel kinematics control work together to meet vehicle dynamics goals. At the vehicle supervisory level, predictive vehicle control uses road information, driver intent, and limits on energy, thermal states, and comfort to create reference paths and set points for the lower layers. Finally, at the mission-control or off-board level, fleet-data-driven tasks optimize operating strategies, parameter settings, and feature configurations over extended time periods, covering trips, routes, and the vehicle's lifetime.

The predictive control solutions from Task T5.1 mainly function at the chassis/powertrain and vehicle supervisory levels. In contrast, the fleet-based mission control functions from Task T5.2 operate at the vehicle supervisory and off-board levels, closing the loop between individual vehicles and the fleet.

From this architectural viewpoint, several background constraints and requirements emerge. The platform must have by-wire interfaces for propulsion, braking, suspension, and steering systems. The vehicle control hardware needs enough processing power to run advanced predictive control algorithms in real-time. The communication links between smart corners and the central controller, as well as between the vehicle and the cloud, must be strong and dependable. Safety and cybersecurity measures must ensure safe operation and protect against unauthorized access. Additionally, the architecture should remain compatible with the digital twin and XiL environments used in WP4 and WP6.

3.2 Control Objectives and Performance Indicators

The developments in deliverable D5.1 are driven by a multi-criteria set of control objectives. These objectives reflect project-level goals related to energy efficiency, safety, comfort, and overall user value. They are translated into quantitative performance indicators, or KPIs, for design and validation.

The first group of objectives focuses on safety and stability. The vehicle must stay stable and controllable in various operating conditions, including low-friction surfaces, emergency manoeuvres, and high loads. Its behaviour must be predictable and compliant with regulatory and original equipment manufacturer (OEM) handling criteria. Additionally, the new control functions must work with existing and future active safety systems like ABS, ESC, traction control, and ADAS.

The second group addresses energy efficiency and range. The control solutions should reduce traction and auxiliary energy use while maintaining safety and comfort. They should maximize energy recuperation by coordinating IWMs and friction brakes. Moreover, they should lower rolling resistance and suspension-induced losses through wheel kinematics and ride-height control.

The third group centres on thermal management and component protection. The temperatures of IWMs, power electronics, and brakes must stay within safe operating limits. The goal is to minimize thermal derating events that cause performance losses or worsen the

user experience. Operational decisions should also consider long-term aging and lifetime factors.

Comfort and noise, vibration, and harshness (NVH) form a fourth group of objectives. The vertical and lateral accelerations experienced by occupants, especially at low to medium speeds, should be limited. Abrupt changes in longitudinal acceleration and jerk must be avoided. The system should use pre-emptive body control based on road preview and, when possible, fleet-derived information on road quality.

The next group of objectives relates to tire utilization and grip management. Vertical tire forces, along with the distribution of lateral and longitudinal forces, should be optimized to increase the usable friction envelope without sacrificing stability. At the same time, tire temperatures and loads should be managed to reduce wear and enhance safety.

Robustness, fault tolerance, and degradation handling are further essential objectives. The control strategies must maintain acceptable performance despite modelling errors, disturbances, and sensor noise. Actuator and sensor faults should be managed through degradation, utilizing redundancy between wheel modules. The controllers must adjust to component aging and changes in vehicle parameters over time.

Finally, the solutions must meet real-time feasibility and complexity requirements. Predictive control and optimization algorithms must run within the available sampling times on embedded hardware, necessitating a careful balance between model fidelity and computational cost. This might involve using surrogate models to reach appropriate trade-offs.

To operationalize these objectives, deliverable D5.1 defines and uses a set of quantitative KPIs. Examples include stability measurements, maximum and RMS longitudinal, lateral, and vertical accelerations in selected manoeuvres, overshoot, settling time, and tracking errors for key variables such as vehicle speed, yaw rate, and ride height. Additional indicators pertain to the user's comfort like vertical accelerations, chassis jerks and body roll. Metrics also gauge computational load and control cycle times on the target ECUs. These KPIs are consistently utilized across simulations, XiL, and, where applicable, vehicle tests to assess and compare control strategies developed in Tasks T5.1 and T5.2.

3.3 Data and Fleet Use Cases

A key aspect of deliverable D5.1 is using data beyond what one vehicle can gather in a single drive. The control solutions are designed to make use of several data categories. On-board data includes signals from vehicle sensors and ECUs, such as kinematic quantities, actuator states, temperatures, driver inputs, and ADAS outputs. Contextual and map data contain high-definition maps, elevation and grade profiles, speed limits, traffic and weather information, and road roughness indices. Fleet data consists of aggregated and anonymized information collected across many vehicles and trips, detailing typical usage patterns, energy consumption, component temperature histories, failure events, and environmental conditions. Additionally, user profile data describe typical driving styles, comfort preferences, and usage patterns for different user segments.

These data sources enable various fleet-based use cases that support the mission-control concepts in Task T5.2 and provide inputs for predictive control in Task T5.1. Energy management that is aware of routes and context becomes possible with fleet-derived consumption models and contextual data, allowing the selection of energy-optimal routes,

speeds, and thermal strategies for upcoming trips. Predictive thermal management can forecast thermal loads based on similar past trips and adjust cooling or heating strategies ahead of time. Road preview and quality estimation benefit from combining map data with fleet observations like accelerations and suspension strokes to predict road grade and roughness, enabling pre-emptive chassis control and comfort optimization. Health monitoring and prognostics use patterns learned from fleet data to detect early signs of degradation or abnormal behaviour in IWMs, power electronics, brakes, and suspension. User-adapted control strategies customize control parameters, such as the balance between comfort and efficiency, based on specific user profiles derived from fleet statistics.

From these use cases, several data-related requirements emerge for the control solutions in deliverable D5.1. Data availability and quality are crucial. On-board measurements must have adequate accuracy, resolution, and synchronization for both control and model identification. Data formats and metadata should be standardized for aggregation and analysis across the fleet. Communication and latency aspects are also vital. Real-time control needs low-latency access to key on-board signals, while the periodic or event-triggered upload of vehicle data to the fleet platform and the download of updated models or control parameters must be organized to avoid interfering with safety-critical functions.

The system must scale well and support robust update mechanisms. Predictive models and control parameters should be trained and updated offline using large fleet datasets. There must be mechanisms to deploy these updates to vehicles in a controlled and traceable manner, for example, through over-the-air updates. Finally, safety, privacy, and cybersecurity requirements must be followed. Safety-critical control loops must remain separate from non-critical data services. Data protection regulations must be adhered to by employing measures such as anonymizing and aggregating fleet data. It is essential to protect against unauthorized access and tampering with control functions or data streams.

These technical background elements and requirements lay the groundwork for the predictive operation of the EV with smart corners in Task T5.1 and the adaptive vehicle mission control using fleet data in Task T5.2, which are detailed in the following sections of this deliverable.

4 Overall Control Architecture

This section describes the overall control architecture created in WP5 and reported in deliverable D5.1. It explains how the different control functions related to predictive operation (Task T5.1) and adaptive, fleet-data-based mission control (Task T5.2) are organized and interconnected. It also outlines how they interact with the SmartCorners hardware platform and off-board services.

The architecture is designed as a hierarchical, modular, and data-driven system. At its core, it combines a real-time vehicle control stack that runs entirely on board with slower optimization and learning processes. These processes use fleet data that can be processed with off-board computation. The on-board stack manages all safety-critical and time-critical functions. It receives measurements from the smart corners and other vehicle subsystems, computes actuator commands, and supervises the vehicle's dynamic behaviour. The off-board components complement this by analysing large volumes of data from many vehicles. They extract models and patterns, then provide updated parameters, calibration data, and high-level strategies.

The design aims to ensure that basic vehicle operation remains robust and safe even without connectivity. Meanwhile, access to fleet data and cloud services gradually improves performance, efficiency, comfort, and adaptability over the vehicle's lifetime. Thus, the architecture follows a “local autonomy plus remote intelligence” approach, with a clear division of responsibilities and interfaces between layers.

4.1 Hierarchical and Functional Decomposition

The overall control architecture has several layers, each with different time scales, computational complexity, and interactions with vehicle hardware. This hierarchical structure helps integrate advanced predictive and optimization methods while maintaining the determinism and safety needed in automotive applications.

At the lowest level, actuator controllers manage direct control of smart corner components and other vehicle actuators. They regulate motor torque, brake pressure, suspension forces, and steering angles based on setpoints received from higher layers. These controllers operate at high sampling rates and generally use straightforward, proven control laws (for example, PI/PID or state-feedback structures), possibly enhanced with feedforward terms and local observers. Their main goal is to ensure accurate tracking, respect actuator limits, and enable local fault detection and protection.

Above the actuator level, a coordinated chassis and powertrain control layer handles interactions between multiple actuators, both within each smart corner and across all four smart corners. Functions like TV, longitudinal and lateral control, vertical force distribution, wheel kinematics optimization, and ride-height control are implemented here. In Task T5.1, this layer deploys NMPC or its variants to leverage road preview, vehicle models, and constraints in a unified optimization framework. Controllers in this layer convert vehicle-level objectives—like desired yaw rate, speed profile, or body motion—into consistent actuator setpoints.

The next level, the vehicle supervisory layer, coordinates behaviour across major subsystems, including powertrain, chassis, and thermal management. It collects data on driver inputs, environment (from ADAS sensors and map data), vehicle states, and constraints (like battery state-of-charge, thermal margins, and component limits). Based on this information, it produces high-level commands such as speed and acceleration targets, path-following references, comfort settings, and operating modes. The predictive operation of the EV with smart corners, developed in Task T5.1, uses this layer to predict driver's trajectory which is used to improve TV performance.

The highest on-board layer is the mission-management layer, which manages trip-level and user-level goals. It determines how to balance energy consumption against travel time and comfort, how to schedule charging stops, and which driving modes and control profiles to apply on different route segments. Although parts of this functionality can run locally, the mission-management layer closely connects with off-board components that provide fleet-based models, predictions, and recommendations. This layer is used in Task T5.2 to send and gather fleet data with the goal to optimize control algorithm performance.

Functionally, the architecture supports both vertical and horizontal integration. Vertically, each control function has a clear place in the hierarchy, from low-level actuation to high-level mission decisions. Horizontally, services such as diagnostics, safety monitoring, cybersecurity

enforcement, and data logging interface with all layers. This integration ensures that the system can be monitored, updated, and validated consistently.

4.2 Integration with Cloud and Off-Board Computing

A key feature of the SmartCorners control architecture is its integration with cloud and off-board computing resources for adaptive, fleet-data-based mission control, as addressed in Task T5.2. This integration uses an off-board computing platform that connects to vehicles through secure communication channels, providing data management, analytics, and model-updating capabilities.

From the vehicle's perspective, the off-board platform appears as a set of services accessed through the connectivity module. Vehicles periodically upload selected data, including aggregated signals, event-based logs, diagnostic information, and performance indicators from past trips. The data is pre-processed on board to reduce bandwidth and ensure privacy and security. Safety-critical control loops do not rely on real-time cloud interaction; instead, cloud interactions happen at relatively low frequencies or asynchronously with the on-board control cycles.

On the server side, data from various vehicles and trips merge to build and refine models of energy consumption, component aging, thermal behaviour, road conditions, and user behaviour. Machine learning and statistical methods derive predictive models and identify typical usage patterns and clusters. Based on these analyses, the platform generates updated calibration data, recommended control parameter sets, and new variants of predictive models tailored to specific vehicle configurations or user segments.

These outputs are then packaged into updates for transmission back to vehicles, such as over-the-air software or calibration updates. Within the vehicle, the mission-management and supervisory layers can load updated models and parameter sets during safe conditions, like when the vehicle is parked. Once updated, the on-board predictive controllers (of Task T5.1) and the mission-control logic (of Task T5.2) can utilize this improved knowledge to achieve better performance and reliability in future trips.

The integration with cloud and off-board computing clearly defines roles. Tasks needing large datasets and heavy computation, like model training and fleet-wide optimization, are performed off-board. Tasks that require precise timing and high reliability, like executing predictive control algorithms in real time, remain on board. The architecture ensures that losing connectivity or cloud service availability leads only to reduced performance, not unsafe behaviour or violations of fundamental requirements.

4.3 Interfaces to Digital Twin and XIL Environments

The control architecture closely connects to the digital twin and XiL environments developed in other WPs. These environments are crucial for designing, tuning, and validating control functions, so their interfaces and data flows must be defined accordingly.

A digital twin of the vehicle equipped with smart corners captures the relevant dynamics of powertrain, chassis, thermal systems, electrical networks, and, when needed, the driver and environment. This digital twin is implemented with varying levels of detail, allowing its use for both offline design and real-time hardware-in-the-Loop (HiL) testing. The same interface definitions governing the interaction between controllers and plant models in the digital twin

are applied in the real vehicle, ensuring that control software can transition smoothly between simulation and implementation.

In a Model-in-the-Loop (MiL) setup, the hierarchical control architecture is executed as software models within the simulation environment. This allows for rapid prototyping of algorithms, exploring parameter spaces, and assessing sensitivity and robustness under various conditions. In Software-in-the-Loop (SiL) and Processor-in-the-Loop (PiL) setups, the actual embedded code intended for the vehicle is executed either in a simulation environment or on target ECUs, interacting with the digital twin plant model. This enables evaluation of real-time performance, resource use, and numerical behaviour.

HiL configurations connect physical control hardware and selected real components (like power electronics modules or smart corner subassemblies) to the digital twin. The architecture and its interfaces are designed to support such setups, ensuring that each control layer can operate with realistic inputs and outputs. Fleet-data-related functions can be validated using recorded data replays and synthetic scenarios generated from the digital twin.

By maintaining consistency among the interfaces used in the real vehicle, including the off-board platform and XiL environments, the overall control architecture supports a smooth development workflow. Controllers and mission-control functions conceived and tested in simulation can be confidently deployed to vehicles, and real-world observations can be used to refine the digital twin and XiL setups. This cycle between design, validation, and deployment supports the continuous improvement of predictive operation and fleet-based mission control throughout the project and beyond.

5 Predictive Operation of EV with SmartCorners (Task T5.1)

The technological advancement in the automotive sector, particularly within EVs, has opened new frontiers for active chassis and vehicle dynamics control. The configuration of an EV equipped with four IWMs and active suspension actuators represents the pinnacle of this evolution, transforming the car from a passive mechanical system into an intelligent, dynamic platform, often encapsulated by the concept of the smart corner. This architecture offers an user-centred level of actuation, but it necessitates a sophisticated and integrated control system to fully exploit its potential. To this purpose, innovative control strategies i.e. NMPC and NN-based model predictive control (NNMPC) will be implemented throughout the project.

The following sections elaborate, the crucial advantages of advanced controllers in the SmartCorners context and the predictive and multi-actuator control strategies that can be implemented to maximize performance, safety, comfort, and energy-efficiency.

5.1 Concept overview

The adoption of IWMs eliminates the need for complex mechanical transmission systems and provides direct and independent torque control for each of the four wheels. This capability, known as TV or FV, is the foundation upon which advanced control strategies are built.

By adding active suspension systems and, crucially, wheel kinematic actuators (for toe and camber) to this configuration, a platform is created with high redundancy and capacity to modulate ground forces (tire-road interaction) in the case study vehicle. However, managing

these multiple, interacting actuators – e.g., IWMs, brakes, suspensions, and kinematics – requires a centralized controller capable of simultaneously optimizing often conflicting objectives, such as safety, performance and passenger comfort.

5.2 Main benefit of advanced integrated chassis controllers

In an EV with IWMs and active suspensions, controllers are no longer simple corrective intervention systems (like traditional ESC), but evolve into pre-emptive and continuously optimizing systems. The aim is to highlight how NMPC, NNMPC, wheel kinematic control, and vertical FV can significantly enhance **vehicle performance, safety, comfort, and energy-efficiency**.

5.2.1 Enhance vehicle performance

Advanced control frameworks provide considerable advantages in terms of vehicle stability, especially in highly dynamic driving scenarios or under adverse road conditions. IWMs enable fully independent torque distribution, allowing rapid and precise modulation of longitudinal and lateral force generation at each corner.

Compared with conventional powertrains, such distributed actuation dramatically reduces system latency and permits sophisticated interventions for understeer/snap-oversteer mitigation, slip control, and lateral stabilization.

Predictive controllers such as NMPC and NNMPC are capable of forecasting vehicle states over a defined time horizon, taking into account real-time measurements, digital maps, ADAS sensor data, and nonlinear chassis dynamics.

This forward-looking capability enables the system to identify potential stability risks and generate pre-emptive corrective actions, thereby enhancing both active safety and the driver's perceived control robustness.

In particular, for performance enhancement purpose, the primary advantage lies in the ability to independently manipulate forces in the road plane to adjust:

- **Yaw moment:** with TV, enabled by the IWMs, it is possible to generate an additional yaw moment (around the vehicle's z-axis) beyond the one provided by steering action. This not only enhances stability in limit conditions (similar to a boosted ESC) but also improves agility and yaw rate tracking precision, enabling the vehicle to follow the desired behaviour with greater fidelity and fewer steering corrections;
- **Vertical load:** with active suspensions, supported by vertical tire FV, implemented with classical controllers, e.g., ground hook, enable the dynamic modification of vertical load distribution among the four wheels, enhancing road-holding, thereby maximizing the lateral grip margin of all four wheels. This effectively pushes the physical limit of the vehicle's lateral capability;
- **Kinematics:** the active control of toe and camber allows the optimal tire contact angle to be maintained relative to the road surface under all dynamic conditions. In cornering, camber adjustment ensures that the entire tire footprint is utilized, maximizing the transmittable lateral force and grip. This is a level of control that passive systems cannot replicate.

5.2.2 Improve active safety and comfort

The integration of data from ADAS and the navigation system enables predictive driving, elevating both comfort and safety through the active suspension system and IWMs.

Active suspensions work to isolate the cabin from road disturbances and actively counteract roll, and pitch, and heave through vertical FV.

Predictive controllers (e.g., NMPC and NNMPC) use the road preview information, e.g. upcoming bumps, curvatures, or uneven surfaces detected by ADAS sensors, to prepare the vehicle before encountering disturbances. This not only enhances safety by maintaining the ideal chassis attitude but also drastically improves ride comfort for passengers, reducing the vehicle body motion.

Other ADAS sensor information, e.g. road friction coefficient, can be used to enhance safety, providing that to the predictive controller, such that motor torques are adjusted to overcome difficult scenarios.

5.2.3 Reduced losses and enhanced energy-efficiency

Advanced controllers, especially predictive ones, are fundamental for energy-efficiency in EVs, where driving range is a critical factor.

- **Rolling resistance minimization:** the wheel kinematic configuration, specifically the control of camber and toe, can be optimized in real-time, based on the vehicle state. In straight-line driving, the controller can adjust these angles to minimize rolling resistance, reducing power dissipation and extending the driving range;
- **Optimal energy recovery:** regenerative braking from the IWMs can be modulated with extreme precision. The controller optimally distributes the braking force between regenerative braking (for battery charging) and mechanical braking (for stability and safety) to maximize energy recovery without compromising dynamic performance;
- **Ride height control:** the ability to regulate the vehicle's ground clearance (ride height control) via active suspensions allows for aerodynamic optimization. At high speeds, lowering the vehicle reduces aerodynamic drag, significantly decreasing energy consumption.

5.3 Predictive integrated chassis control architecture

The core of the proposed pre-emptive chassis control architecture is the NMPC, which predicts the future evolution of vehicle states using nonlinear full-vehicle models and computes optimal control inputs accordingly. In the proposed implementation, the NMPC framework may directly regulate:

- Individual wheel torques;
- Vertical suspension forces;
- Wheel kinematic angles.

The ability to coordinate simultaneously these heterogeneous actuators results in holistic vehicle behaviour optimization over a so called “predictive horizon”. NMPC inherently manages the system's operating constraints, such as the physical limits of motor torque,

suspension travel, maximum kinematic actuator angles, and, critically, the available tire grip limit.

In this perspective, NMPC becomes pre-emptive when it receives future data (road preview, navigation data and ADAS sensors). If the controller "knows" a tight curve is approaching in 2 seconds, it can start pre-loading the suspensions or pre-adjusting the camber in advance, ensuring a smoother and safer dynamic transition.

5.3.1 Vertical force vectoring and body control

Vertical tire FV involves the active allocation of normal forces among the four wheels to improve global chassis behaviour, both in terms of comfort and performance.

By adjusting vertical loads, the controller can:

- Optimize available lateral and longitudinal grip;
- Reduce unbalanced load transfer;
- Enhance stability during cornering;
- Minimize wheel slip and undesired oscillations.

This approach enables the system to modulate the vehicle's dynamic characteristics proactively, especially when integrated with road preview.

To this purpose, the ride height control system proposed within Task T5.1 adopts a hierarchical structure:

1. **Low-level roll and pitch tracking:** a high-bandwidth controller stabilizes roll and pitch angles, ensuring rapid response to road disturbances and dynamic manoeuvres;
2. **High-Level controller for ride height planning:** this supervisory layer defines the desired vertical plan based on navigation data, road profile prediction, and vehicle state estimation, e.g., lowering the vehicle at high speed for aerodynamic efficiency or increasing ground clearance on irregular roads.

This hierarchical approach ensures both responsiveness and strategic optimization of vehicle body posture.

5.3.2 Wheel kinematic control

SmartCorners modules allow active adjustment of key wheel kinematic parameters.

- **Toe control:** affects vehicle directional response and rolling resistance;
- **Camber control:** maximizes tire effectiveness during cornering by adjusting the contact patch geometry.

The combined regulation of these angles provides unprecedented manipulation of vehicle dynamics, enabling energy savings, enhanced trajectory tracking, and improved handling performance.

5.3.3 Real-time implementation

The main limitation of NMPC is the high computational cost of real-time optimization, especially over long-time horizons or with highly complex vehicle models. To address this problem, surrogate models based on NNs are introduced. These models approximate the

nonlinear vehicle dynamics with high accuracy while significantly reducing computation time, ensuring real-time implementability.

To SmartCorners purposes, an IL toolchain will be implemented to copy the NMPC behaviour with a NN that will be tested on project demonstrators. As specified in the Grant Agreement, the surrogate models must be carefully evaluated and validated to ensure that their simplification does not introduce unacceptable errors into the controller's predictive behaviour.

5.4 Preliminary results

The first set of results coming from simulations run on the global model obtained in Task T1.3, showing the benefits coming from the Rear Wheel Steering (RWS) control action – applied to the Ioniq 5 vehicle model – on the yaw rate tracking. The yaw rate reference is calculated from the manoeuvre parameters, such as steering wheel amplitude, accelerator and braking pedal request and reference vehicle speed, and it is used as main KPI for preliminary analysis of the performance. Applying a non-zero δ_R to the Ioniq 5 vehicle model, causes a reduction of $\sim 50\%$ of maximum yaw rate tracking error with respect to the passive vehicle, which is the Ioniq 5 vehicle as it is, without any additional control action (no TV, no active camber, no active RWS).

Figure 1: Simulation results during a sinusoidal steering manoeuvre in terms of RWS control action amplitude (left side) and yaw rate tracking performance (right side).

5.5 Next steps

The main goal of Task T5.1 is to embed the pre-emptive integrated chassis control strategy, described in Section 5.3, in the global model obtained in Task T1.3 and described in deliverable D1.3, which includes all the sub models provided by the project partners. To achieve this task, in the next weeks all the integrated chassis control action (similarly to RWS case) will be applied to the global model, and their performance will be evaluated through different manoeuvres and scenarios, highlighting the benefits coming from the SmartCorners system. The set of comprehensive results will be included in deliverable D5.4, in M34.

6 Adaptive Vehicle Mission Control Using Fleet Data (Task T5.2)

Task T5.2 extends the control architecture by adding a mission-level layer that exploits fleet data to enhance predictive operation. This additional layer uses information collected from connected test (fleet) vehicles and combines it with the on-board predictive controllers

developed in WP4 and WP5. The objective, in line with the project description, is to obtain control strategies that are tailored both to individual user profiles and to the statistical knowledge gathered from many vehicles through vehicle-to-everything (V2X) communication and cloud computing. This task builds on Task T5.1 and roll control is treated as a special case of TV. Here, the TV objective is formulated to minimize vehicle roll, rather than to control yaw rate and side slip angle as discussed in Task T5.1.

For roll control, Task T5.2 effectively turns the fleet into a distributed sensor network. Each vehicle continuously estimates road friction and roughness and computes comfort-related KPIs. These structured data are uploaded to the cloud analytics platform, where they are aggregated and post-processed. Subsequent vehicles can then download compact road descriptors and use them to adapt their predictive roll control in advance, which improves ride comfort and safety compared with an architecture that relies solely on local, instantaneous measurements.

6.1 Concept Overview

Task T5.2 builds on the torque-based “Virtual Active Rollbar” concept introduced in WP4. In this control approach, the IWMs generate differential longitudinal forces between the left and right sides of the vehicle. Owing to the suspension geometry, part of these forces is converted into vertical wheel loads, which produces an active roll moment without requiring mechanical anti-roll bars.

In the WP4 simulation demonstrator, this control approach already achieved a substantial reduction of body roll during slalom manoeuvres. The holonic controller developed there lowered RMS roll angle by roughly half compared with the passive vehicle and a conventional P-controller, while preserving pitch behaviour and avoiding excessive roll-rate oscillations. These results confirmed that vertical FV with IWMs is an effective actuator concept for managing chassis posture and perceived comfort.

Task T5.2 extends this foundation in three directions (Figure 2). First, a surface-grip estimation module is introduced so that each vehicle can behave as a road-grip sensor, providing estimates of local friction and roughness in real-time. Second, the resulting signals, together with relevant KPIs and context information, are transferred to the cloud, where they are stored, filtered and combined into a road-condition map. Third, the predictive roll-control algorithm is enhanced so that it can consume these fleet-derived road descriptors in addition to its local preview information, allowing the controller to refine its optimisation beyond what is possible with on-board prediction alone.

In the resulting closed loop, vehicles no longer depend exclusively on their own estimates of the current road state. When planning or executing a trip, the mission-control layer queries a cloud-based “road-intelligence” service that is continuously updated with friction and comfort information from earlier vehicles that have driven the same segments. This service returns anticipated friction levels and road-quality indicators along the route. The on-board mission controller can then adjust roll-control parameters before the vehicle reaches a demanding curve or a rough section, enabling a truly predictive roll and comfort control strategy that benefits from the collective experience of the fleet.

Figure 2: High level control concept overview

It is important to clarify that fleet data is only used to adjust the comfort and performance balance of the roll controller. It cannot compromise occupant safety. By design, the information received from the cloud can only make the roll-control action more conservative. For instance, this can happen by reducing the amount of longitudinal torque used to create corrective vertical load transfer and roll moment. Using smaller longitudinal force interventions naturally increases the safety margin. This is because it cuts down tire-force use and the risk of hitting friction limits. This design choice is vital since fleet information may be flawed or unavailable due to issues like network delays, limited coverage, outdated data, or even deliberate tampering. As a result, the safety-critical stability constraints and fallback strategies stay entirely on board. The vehicle maintains safe behaviour regardless of the fleet data it receives. In the worst-case scenario, reduced or unreliable fleet information leads to decreased roll comfort performance instead of unsafe operation.

6.2 Predictive Roll Control Architecture

In the proposed implementation, roll control is designed to be both reactive and predictive, because passenger comfort is affected by fast, local disturbances as well as by slower, foreseeable vehicle motions. The reactive component responds immediately to changes in road excitation and operating conditions, in particular to vertical road variations (bumps, patch transitions, unevenness) and to sudden changes in surface grip. These events are only partially predictable and can appear with little warning, so the controller must rely on high-bandwidth feedback signals and robust on-board estimation to adjust the applied IWM torque split and the resulting roll moment in real-time. In practice, this reactive loop stabilises the roll dynamics against disturbances and ensures that the controller remains well-behaved when the actual road deviates from what was expected.

In parallel, the predictive component anticipates the upcoming roll demand by estimating future roll-relevant states over a short horizon. This prediction is driven by measurable signals

that precede roll build-up, most importantly the steering wheel angle (as a proxy for the driver's intended curvature), the measured lateral acceleration (as an indicator of current lateral load transfer and cornering intensity), and the roll angle (capturing the current posture and dynamic state of the sprung mass). Using these inputs, the predictive controller forecasts how roll angle, roll rate and roll acceleration will evolve in the near future and computes a torque strategy that shapes the roll response proactively, rather than merely correcting it after large roll excursions have already occurred.

Both approaches are required because neither alone can deliver robust comfort improvements across real-world conditions. A purely reactive strategy can mitigate disturbances once they occur, but it tends to act late in manoeuvres: e.g. roll peaks are only countered after roll has already developed, which typically increases roll-rate and roll-acceleration transients and can be perceived as “busy” or jerky by occupants. Conversely, a purely predictive strategy can perform well during smooth, repeatable manoeuvres, but it is inherently sensitive to modelling errors and unanticipated disturbances, such as local road unevenness or abrupt friction changes; without a reactive stabilising layer it may generate inappropriate torque actions and degrade comfort. The combined architecture therefore uses prediction to plan smooth, early roll compensation during cornering, while the reactive feedback loop provides disturbance rejection and robustness, guaranteeing acceptable behaviour even when the road, grip, or measured signals differ from expectations.

6.3 Surface Grip Estimation

A key enabler for fleet-supported mission control is the ability of each vehicle to estimate the locally available tire–road friction in everyday driving. In the SmartCorners architecture, this information is obtained primarily through a reactive slip-control layer that supervises the IWM torque commands and intervenes whenever the requested longitudinal tire force approaches the available grip.

The slip-control function monitors wheel speeds and vehicle motion to estimate longitudinal slip at each wheel. When the predictive roll controller (or any other supervisory function) requests a torque that is too high for the current road surface, the wheel begins to deviate from the expected rolling condition. In traction, this manifests as a rapid increase of positive slip and a wheel “spin-up”. In regenerative braking, it appears as excessive negative slip and a tendency toward wheel “lock-up”. In both cases, slip control reacts on a fast time scale by reducing (or saturating) the applied motor torque so that the wheel returns to a stable slip region and the tire remains within its friction capability. This intervention prevents loss of longitudinal force authority, avoids unnecessary tire wear and maintains directional stability.

Beyond its direct safety and drivability role, the reactive slip-control action provides a practical, continuously available mechanism for surface grip estimation. When torque limiting occurs, the vehicle has effectively observed that the demanded tire force exceeded what the road can support under the current normal load and operating conditions. By relating the commanded torque (and thus the requested longitudinal force), the observed slip behaviour, and estimates of vertical wheel load, the system can infer an estimate of the maximum usable friction level. These observations are aggregated to produce a robust estimate of local grip.

Each grip estimate is time-stamped and associated with vehicle position and context metadata. Typical metadata include global positioning system (GPS) coordinates (optionally map-matched to road segments), ambient conditions if available, and time of measurements.

Comfort-relevant context, such as whether the vehicle was undergoing a cornering manoeuvre, can also be included, since lateral load transfer influences available longitudinal force margin.

Once uploaded, the cloud platform aggregates grip estimates from multiple vehicles and multiple passes over the same road sections. This produces a fleet-level road-friction layer that characterises typical μ levels and their variability per segment and condition. Subsequent vehicles can query this information and use it as a prior for their on-board friction estimation and for configuring the constraints of the predictive roll controller. Importantly, because the slip controller operates locally and reactively, it remains the ultimate safeguard: regardless of what friction information is received from the cloud, any excessive torque request is still clipped in real-time to prevent wheel spin-up in traction or wheel lock-up under regenerative braking.

6.4 Fleet Data Integration

Fleet data is integrated into the roll-control function to improve passenger comfort by enabling earlier, smoother control actions. The key idea is that comfort is degraded not only by large roll angles, but also by rapid changes in roll-related states, especially roll rate and roll acceleration, which are perceived as “harshness”. Purely reactive control tends to intervene only after a disturbance has already occurred or after the vehicle has already entered a corner with a certain lateral load transfer. When the controller reacts late, it must apply relatively abrupt torque corrections to recover the desired roll behaviour. These sudden changes in wheel torque propagate through driveline dynamics and tire forces into the vehicle body and are experienced by occupants as longitudinal and lateral jerk, as well as high-frequency roll acceleration. In other words, even if reactive control protects against wheel spin or stabilises roll motion, its delayed and discontinuous interventions can introduce comfort penalties.

Fleet data helps to resolve this limitation by providing predictive context about upcoming road conditions. Grip estimates (Section 6.3) and roughness indicators gathered from other vehicles are aggregated into a road-intelligence layer that is indexed by location and, when possible, driving direction and environment context. When a vehicle approaches a road segment that is known (based on fleet observations) to have reduced friction or high excitation (bumps, repaired patches, uneven asphalt), the mission-control layer can pre-configure the predictive roll controller before the disturbance is encountered. Instead of waiting for slip control to trigger torque limiting, the controller can proactively reshape its optimisation problem by tightening friction constraints, adjusting roll-angle targets, and modifying comfort-related weights. This causes the resulting torque strategy to ramp more gradually and to avoid operating close to saturation, thereby reducing the likelihood of abrupt reactive interventions.

In practice, the predictive model uses the fleet-derived information as a prior for the near-future road state. For low- μ segments, the controller plans roll compensation with larger safety margins and smoother torque profiles, which reduces the need for fast corrective torque cuts by the slip controller. For rough segments, the controller can reduce high-frequency roll tracking effort and favour a more compliant posture response, preventing the “chasing” behaviour that would otherwise increase jerk. This also improves consistency, because the control behaviour becomes location-aware and repeatable: the vehicle behaves similarly each time it traverses a known segment, rather than producing variable reactive corrections depending on the exact moment at which disturbances are detected.

Overall, fleet-data integration turns the control strategy from “react, then limit” into “anticipate, then act smoothly”. The reactive layer remains essential as a safety and robustness backstop, but the primary comfort improvement comes from shifting interventions earlier in time and distributing them over the prediction horizon. As a result, the vehicle achieves comparable or better roll reduction with smaller torque transients, fewer slip-control events, and reduced perceived jerk, while maintaining safe operation even when fleet information is unavailable or uncertain.

6.5 Predictive Control Vehicle Testing Results

The predictive roll-control concept was validated on the ELAPHE demonstrator vehicle in a dedicated proving-ground campaign. The objective of these tests was to confirm that the comfort benefits observed in simulation translate to real vehicle dynamics, tire behaviour and actuator limitations, and to evaluate the robustness of the controller when exposed to road irregularities and local grip variations that cannot be perfectly reproduced in a simulation environment.

Testing was conducted on a closed track section with repeated manoeuvres along the same corridor, enabling a consistent comparison between different controller tunings and objective functions. The recorded GPS trajectory

(

Figure 3), colour-coded by vehicle speed, confirms that the vehicle followed a repeatable path with comparable velocity levels across the evaluated runs, which is a prerequisite for a meaningful comfort comparison between tuning variants. The time histories measured during the manoeuvres show the expected periodic cornering excitation, with steering input leading the lateral response, followed by the roll response of the sprung mass.

Figure 3: Slalom test cases overlaid

Roll-related measurements demonstrate that the predictive controller achieves roll mitigation comparable to the simulation demonstrator. The measured roll angle exhibits a clear reduction in peak-to-peak magnitude and improved uniformity across successive left–right transitions, while roll rate and roll acceleration are shaped to avoid excessive transients (Figure 4). This is important from a comfort perspective, as occupants are particularly sensitive to rapid changes in roll dynamics rather than to quasi-static roll alone. Across the tested controller variants, the tuning targeted at roll dynamics (roll rate / roll acceleration) shows the expected reduction of sharp peaks in roll acceleration, which indicates smoother body motion and reduced perceived harshness during rapid steering reversals (Figure 5).

Figure 4: Comparison of roll, roll rate and roll acceleration during slalom manoeuvre

Figure 5: Spider chart comparing different roll control tuning KPIs

The wider set of vehicle signals confirms that these comfort improvements are achieved without inducing unstable tire behaviour. Logged wheel-speed and slip signals remain within acceptable boundaries, and the reactive slip supervision intervenes only in short, localised events, indicating that the predictive controller generally avoids operating near the longitudinal friction limits (Figure 6). This aligns with the design intent of Task T5.2: fleet-derived grip information and on-board estimation are used to keep the optimisation away from saturation regions, thereby reducing the number of abrupt torque-limit events that would otherwise introduce jerk. In the measured data, the requested and realised wheel-torque profiles show that the controller distributes corrective action over time rather than relying on short, high-amplitude interventions, which is consistent with a predictive optimisation strategy.

Figure 6: Slip control activation

To enable objective comparison of controller variants, comfort and stability KPIs were computed from the measurement time series. These KPIs include inverse RMS values of roll angle, roll rate and roll acceleration, as well as metrics related to longitudinal slip and the number of smart corner activation events (Figure 5). The KPI summary indicates that the vehicle results follow the same trend as the simulation: roll comfort improves significantly relative to baseline tuning, and different controller weightings shift the balance between maximum roll suppression and smoothness (i.e., reduced roll acceleration). In particular, the best-performing comfort-oriented tunings achieve the combined effect of reducing roll response while also limiting high-frequency content in roll acceleration, which is critical for passenger perception.

Overall, the vehicle campaign confirms that predictive roll control with IWM-based vertical force vectoring is feasible in real driving conditions and delivers comfort improvements consistent with simulation results. The tests also provide a validated dataset (containing roll dynamics, slip supervision activity, torque requests and GPS-referenced context) that can be directly used in the Task T5.2 fleet pipeline: the measured road-dependent grip and comfort indicators can be uploaded to the cloud, aggregated by location, and reused as priors for

subsequent vehicles to further reduce reactive interventions and improve comfort repeatability on the same route.

6.6 Roadmap and Next Steps

Deliverable D5.1 is planned as an intermediate deliverable reporting the ongoing work in Task T5.1 and Task T5.2. It captures the status at M24, including the key architectural choices, the first implementations, and the initial validation activities. The final reporting and consolidated results of Tasks T5.1 and T5.2 will be handled in Deliverable D5.4 (M34).

Within the scope reported in deliverable D5.1, the main high-risk control challenges have been addressed to de-risk the later integrated demonstrations. Predictive roll control has been implemented and shown to operate on the vehicle with improvements consistent with prior simulation trends. The connection to the cloud infrastructure has been established, enabling upload of structured measurements and KPIs and providing the basis for fleet-data usage. In addition, the reactive slip-control layer can detect surface-grip limitations by identifying when requested wheel torque exceeds the available friction and must be limited to avoid wheel spin-up (or lock-up under regenerative torque). Finally, the predictive roll controller has been extended to accept grip-limitation information as an input, allowing it to adapt constraints and avoid overly aggressive corrective actions when friction is limited.

The next phase towards M34 will focus on completing and demonstrating the end-to-end concept and expanding validation. The primary objective is to deliver a proof-of-concept where surface-grip estimation, cloud-based aggregation, road-segment annotation and vehicle-side consumption of fleet-derived grip information are connected in a closed loop. In parallel, additional simulation campaigns and proving-ground tests will be carried out to cover a wider range of manoeuvres, surface conditions and environmental scenarios, and to quantify benefits consistently using the agreed KPI set. These integrated results, together with the final conclusions for Tasks T5.1 and T5.2, will be documented in deliverable D5.4 at M34.

7 Contribution to Project Objectives, Milestones and Impacts

This deliverable contributes directly to the SmartCorners objective of enabling a user-centric, AI-supported and predictive vehicle-level control strategy that exploits historical and current data from the vehicle, its environment and relevant fleets to improve operation. The work reported in deliverable D5.1 concretely advances WP5 “Optimal, safe and secure operation on vehicle level”, which targets predictive control strategies for enhanced dynamic performance, user-centric mission adjustment using offboard fleet data, fault-tolerant operation and cybersecurity/data protection considerations. In particular, first set of results related to the integrated chassis pre-emptive control, show evident benefits during high demanding manoeuvre. In addition, the reported implementation and initial validation of predictive roll control, its extension to accept grip-limitation inputs from the slip-control layer, and the establishment of the cloud connection for uploading structured measurements and KPIs provide early building blocks for bridging on-board predictive controllers with off-board data services.

In terms of milestones, deliverable D5.1 is explicitly listed as a means of verification for Milestone 4: “Control strategy available” due at M24, together with deliverable D6.1. The

results in this report therefore serve as evidence that core control concepts have matured from design into first implementation and initial validation, de-risking the subsequent integrated demonstrations and evaluations.

Regarding project impacts, the outcomes reported here support the call's expected impact of accelerating the uptake of user-centric and optimised EV solutions by enabling software-defined, adaptable vehicle behaviour that integrates comfort and safety functions through advanced control. Specifically for chassis and ride-quality topics, the ability to perform predictive body control and to adapt behaviour based on offboard "road intelligence" derived from fleet sensing is aligned with the project's ambition to improve ride quality through vibration suppression and optimal control of comfort-related functions. By establishing the fleet-to-cloud pipeline and demonstrating vehicle operation of predictive control functions, deliverable D5.1 enables technology toward the broader SmartCorners impact pathway that couples innovative EV topology with AI-based, predictive and personalised operation.

Finally, the safety and robustness framing adopted in deliverable D5.1 is consistent with WP5's explicit scope covering cybersecurity and data protection, since offboard data is treated as an advisory input that can only scale back aggressiveness of comfort-focused actuation while the controller remains safe under missing, outdated or compromised connectivity. This "safe-by-design" use of fleet data supports responsible deployment of connected control functions and prepares the ground for the later consolidated demonstrations and reporting.

8 Conclusion

Deliverable D5.1 reports the status of the ongoing work in Task T5.1 and T5.2 at M24, focusing on the vehicle-level control building blocks needed for predictive operation of the SmartCorners EV and for fleet-data-supported mission adaptation. The deliverable consolidates the control architecture developed in WP5 and demonstrates that the key concepts have progressed from design to working implementations suitable for further integration and validation.

On the vehicle side, proof-of-concept integrated chassis controller is in progress, with available results related to the RWS control action applied to the global model obtained from Task T1.3. Moreover, predictive roll control based on IWMs actuation has been implemented and validated in proving-ground tests, showing roll-comfort improvements consistent with prior simulation trends. The controller combines a predictive layer, which anticipates cornering-induced roll demand from steering input and measured vehicle states, with a reactive layer that handles unforeseen disturbances such as local vertical road excitation and abrupt surface changes. This combination enables both smooth comfort-oriented behaviour and robustness against modelling errors and real-world disturbances.

In parallel, slip control has been implemented as a fast supervisory layer ensuring safe tire-force utilisation. Besides preventing wheel spin-up in traction and wheel lock-up under regenerative torque, the slip-control intervention logic provides a practical indication of local friction limitations. This information can be used to tighten constraints and moderate roll-actuation requests in the predictive controller, improving comfort by reducing abrupt torque corrections and the associated jerk.

Finally, the vehicle-to-cloud connection has been established to support fleet data collection. Together, these elements form the technical basis for the Task T5.2 concept, in which vehicles act as distributed sensors for road grip and roughness, and fleet-derived “road intelligence” is used to adapt predictive roll control ahead of critical road segments. The next project phase will focus on closing this loop end-to-end and expanding validation in simulation and vehicle testing, while the final consolidated reporting for Tasks T5.1 and T5.2 will be provided in deliverable D5.4 at M34.

8.1 Deviations, Impact and Recovery Actions

At M24, no critical deviations have been identified that would prevent achieving the objectives of Tasks T5.1 and T5.2 by M34.

9 Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Long text
ABS	Anti-lock Braking System
ADAS	Advanced Driver Assistance Systems
AI	Artificial Intelligence
BEV	Battery Electric Vehicle
ECU	Electronic Control Unit
ESC	Electronic Stability Control
EV	Electric Vehicle
FV	Force Vectoring
GPS	Global Positioning System
HiL	Hardware-in-the-Loop
IL	Imitation Learning
IWM	In-Wheel Motor
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
MiL	Model-in-the-Loop
NNMPC	Neural-Network Model Predictive Control
NMPC	Nonlinear Model Predictive Control
NN	Neural Network
NNMPC	Neural-Network Model Predictive Control
NVH	Noise, Vibration, and Harshness
OEM	Original Equipment Manufacturer
PiL	Processor-in-the-Loop
PU	Public
RMS	Root Mean Square
RWS	Rear Wheel Steering
SiL	Software-in-the-Loop
TV	Torque Vectoring
V2X	Vehicle-to-Everything
WP	Work Package
XiL	X-in-the-Loop
μ	Tire-road friction coefficient

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